
8. Why radial velocities?

THE SCIENTIFIC GOALS of ESA's Hipparcos mission, as they were prioritised at the time, were set out in ESA's Phase A study into the mission's feasibility in 1979. Priorities included defining a better stellar reference system, and providing a framework of improved distances, luminosities, and proper motions.

Radial velocities as a crucial observational quantity, and as a complement to the Hipparcos astrometry data, began to be discussed around the same time, especially in France and Switzerland. Indeed, the Phase A study report (pp19–20) made explicit reference to their importance. The compilation of measurements was duly identified as a task for the mission preparation, as described in the proposal for the 'input catalogue' to ESA in 1982.

But funding authorities were unwilling to support dedicated facilities, and acquiring even a limited subset of radial velocities proved to be a challenge.

KNOWING A STAR'S radial velocity is important because classical astrometry cannot measure a star's complete motion in space. And this applies to both Hipparcos and Gaia as well. Specifically, positional measurements can fix the star's position on the sky and its distance, in other words its full three-dimensional coordinate. But they can measure only the *projected* motion of the star across the sky (its proper motion).

The third component of the star's space velocity can only be determined from its radial velocity. Without it, the star's complete space motion is unknown, and kinematic and dynamical insights of individual objects – and entire populations – are accordingly restricted.

Multiple radial velocity measures can yield information on orbits and orbital companions (whether stars or planets), which themselves will distort knowledge of the star's space motion. But even a single radial velocity measure would provide much valuable information.

By 1982, with the solicitation for observing proposals on which the Hipparcos catalogue would eventually be based, the breadth of its scientific case was becoming more evident. And the importance and urgency of acquiring radial velocity measurements began to be discussed more widely (e.g. Fehrenbach 1985).

RADIAL VELOCITY observations for a fairly limited subset of the Hipparcos stars were eventually made. These had to compete for telescope time and instrumentation in both northern and southern hemispheres. The effort was substantial, and a brief summary is given here. Further details are given in my *Astronomical Applications of Astrometry* (2009, pp32–35).

For early-type stars in the northern hemisphere, Charles Fehrenbach began a radial velocities survey for Hipparcos candidate stars in around 1982 using telescopes at the Observatoire de Haute Provence (OHP), in southern France. By the end of the programme, about 60% of the 12 000 B5–F5 stars in the northern part of the Hipparcos survey had radial velocities.

For early-type stars in the southern hemisphere, two ESO key-programmes for B5–F5 stars were started at the end of 1988 at the 1.52-m ESO telescope at La Silla: one for early-type stars nearer than 100 pc, and one for early-type stars in OB and early-A associations.

For late-type stars in the northern hemisphere, a programme of Coravel measurements using the 1-m Swiss telescope at OHP had been ongoing since 1977. It was dedicated, independently of Hipparcos, to nearby stars, cluster stars, high proper motion stars, Cepheids, and visual binaries, many of which would eventually be included in the Hipparcos programme.

For late-type stars in the southern hemisphere, an ESO key-programme was accepted in January 1989 for approximately 20 000 stars later than F5, using Coravel-South on the 1.54-m Danish telescope at La Silla. The overall observing programme was constructed along similar lines as for the northern part, and comprised Hipparcos 'survey' stars and various high-priority Galactic study programmes, all with two observations per star. Observations, totalling some 200 ESO and 200 Danish telescope nights, continued until about mid-1995.

Restrictions on the wider access to some of these results, meant that only about 20 000 radial velocities could be made more widely available at the time of the Hipparcos catalogue release. Acquiring them had been a major effort, but they represented only a small fraction of the total number of 120 000 Hipparcos stars.

IT IS PERHAPS of some historical interest to summarise the steps that were taken in trying to set up *dedicated* radial velocity measurement facilities at the time. This background, from my own records as ESA's project scientist, and those of Catherine Turon (Observatoire de Paris–Meudon), underlines how much work was invested in attempts to acquire them, the difficulties that were encountered, and the attitudes towards the importance of radial velocities that existed at the time.

ALREADY IN 1979, Catherine Turon, who would go on to lead the consortium defining the scientific priorities and catalogue content, had estimated the total number of radial velocity measurements that would be required to support the Hipparcos programme.

In 1980, a proposal was made by Albert Bijaoui to INAG (now INSU) in France for a new telescope and associated instrumentation, Coravel–North, to be installed at the Observatoire de Haute Provence, at an estimated cost of 5 MFrancs (say, 1.7M€ today). It would improve the existing Coravel limiting magnitude from $B < 14$ to 15.5, and would extend observations to A–F-type stars. At that time, the number of Hipparcos stars with no reliable radial velocity was estimated to be some 34 000 out of some 60 000 survey stars, and some 25 000 out of 40 000 non-survey stars with $B = 9 - 13$, corresponding to around 6 years of dedicated observations, assuming 3 observations per star. This proposal, and an updated proposal in September 1981, were unsuccessful.

IN JANUARY 1982, a meeting in Marseille between Marcel Golay, Michel Mayor and Fredy Rufener from Geneva Observatory, James Lequeux, Marc Azzopardi, Louis Prévot and Yvon Georgelin from Marseille Observatory, Renaud Foy and Guy Monnet from Lyon Observatory, Albert Bijaoui from Nice Observatory, and Suzanne Grenier and Catherine Turon from Paris Observatory, continued to emphasise the importance of radial velocities being available at the time of the Hipparcos catalogue publication, estimated then as around 1991.

They decreased the target observations per star to 2, and formulated a plan for a southern hemisphere programme of 12 000 observations per year for 5–6 years, with 6000 observations per year in the northern hemisphere. Given that some observations had already been made with the OHP Coravel, and that further northern hemisphere observations could start immediately, both goals were considered achievable within 10 years.

A new southern 1.5 m telescope was proposed as a collaboration between ESO, Geneva, and INAG, at a cost of 4 MFrancs (say, 1.4M€). The proposal, presented to ESO by James Lequeux and Michel Mayor in May 1982, was also unsuccessful. Nevertheless, these requests probably helped the decision to build the Elodie spectrograph for the 1.93 m telescope at OHP.

IN 1987, two years before launch, Roger Griffin, of the Institute of Astronomy, Cambridge, took up the challenge and submitted a proposal to the UK funding body, the SERC (now STFC) to acquire radial velocities for the Hipparcos stars and, in any telescope time still available, the Tycho stars. The proposal called for two identical 1-m telescopes, one in each hemisphere, at a total cost of about 1 M£ (say, 2M€ today). As he stated, *'The Hipparcos results will be made infinitely more valuable by the provision of radial velocities to complement the transverse motions measured by the satellite.'*

The proposal was supported by many, including Adriaan Blaauw as chair of the Hipparcos Proposal Selection Committee, Catherine Turon as chair of the INCA Consortium, and me as Project Scientist. But two separate proposal submissions were, again, unsuccessful.

I also made the science case to senior ESA management. It was again rejected, on the grounds that ESA had no mandate to fund ground-based astronomy, and these sorts of supporting measurements should be made from the ground. We had reached the final impasse.

MANY PROGRAMMES were later undertaken with existing instruments. But the systematic acquisition of radial velocities for all Hipparcos stars, in time for inclusion in the published catalogue, was a vision which, while articulated by many, never came to fruition.

Many papers using the Hipparcos data, from 1997 onwards, nevertheless remarked on their absence. Would it not have been a good idea, they implied, to have acquired and published radial velocities along with the final astrometric and photometric catalogues?!

In the years since, and with Gaia in mind, major ground-based programmes have contributed substantially, with the southern-hemisphere RAVE survey, at the UK Schmidt telescope in Australia, contributing radial velocities for 450 000 stars between 2003–213.

THESE PROTRACTED EXPERIENCES were central to my efforts in getting radial velocity measurements, for as many stars as possible, included as part of Gaia during the study phase before the mission's approval in 2000.

Doing so onboard would give measurements at the same time as the astrometric and photometric observations were being made for each star. Eventually, from an instrument point of view, observing all stars to a faint limit of about 13 mag would prove to be feasible.

FAST FORWARD to today, and EDR3 includes more than 7 million stars measured by Gaia, to 0.2–3 km s⁻¹.

But how were we able to clinch the case for these measurements to be made (and funded) as part of Gaia – when this had failed so dismally for Hipparcos?

That, my friends, is a story that can be told in just one minute, but it will have to wait for some other time!